

The Relationship between Transformational Leadership Style, Work Motivation and Work Performance of Civil Servants at the People's Committee of Cam Lam District

Phan Dinh Phung

Ba Ria Vung Tau University

ABSTRACT: The study was conducted to test the relationship between leadership style, work motivation and work performance of civil servants at the People's Committee of Cam Lam district. Thereby, the topic aims to contribute to building a transformational leadership style, increasing work motivation and work efficiency of civil servants at the People's Committee of Cam Lam district. The thesis uses qualitative research methods combined with quantitative research. The study shows the positive relationship between the transformational leadership style factors, work motivation and work efficiency. Transformational leadership style has a positive impact on work motivation and work performance, and work motivation also has a positive impact on work performance. Work motivation plays a part as a mediator between transformational leadership styles and performance. The research results are meaningful to help leaders of Cam Lam District People's Committee improve their transformational leadership style, increase work motivation to bring about work efficiency. The study gives some managerial implications and limitations of the topic and directions for further research.

KEYWORD: Transformational leadership style, work motivation and performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many factors affecting the performance of civil servants such as: working environment, leadership style, work pressure, capacity level and sense of responsibility of each employee; in which, leadership style has the strongest impact on employee performance (Bass and Avolio, 1990). Drucker (1993) asserted that leadership style is the most important factor for organizational success. Bass and Avolio (1990) further concretize the importance of leadership style when they show that leadership style determines between 45% and 65% of the success or failure of an organization.

Thus, leadership style plays a very important role for agencies and organizations. There are many studies on the impact of leadership style, but only analyzed and evaluated on satisfaction, loyalty (Tran Thi Thu Trang, 2006) and employee engagement in the organization (Nguyen Thi Hong Hanh)., 2008). A few only study the impact of leadership style on the performance of employees in enterprises and companies in the business field (Tran Viet Hoang Nguyen, 2014).

Currently, there is little research on the impact of leadership style on the performance of public servants. While the contingent of civil servants at commune level has a very important role in ensuring the successful implementation of guidelines and policies of the Party and State in the fields of politics, economy, society, national defense and security. . Therefore, the topic "The relationship between leadership style, work motivation and work efficiency of civil servants at Cam Lam District People's Committee" aims to contribute to improving leadership capacity, creating work motivation. good to bring efficiency to the work of civil servants.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1. Transformational leadership style

Greenleaf (1977) argues that: on the basis of being a servant of the people, the leader is a servant and focuses on meeting the needs of the people. Researchers have affirmed that building public servanthood and building transformational leadership have similarities. Public servants have a lot in common with transformational leader's personal intellectual exploration and stimulation (Van, 2011).

The transformational leadership style is one of the most influential leadership models of Burns (1978). He describes transformational leadership as the process in which "leaders and followers interact to increase levels of morale and motivation."

Therefore, he sees transformational leadership as being "inherently tied to higher-order values". Then, Bass and colleagues continued to study and explain, transformational leadership is mainly the impact of the leader on employees, helping employees feel trust, admiration, loyalty, and respect. In which the leader encourages employees to work more than originally planned. The leader also encourages employees to perceive that work results are for the benefit of the organization as a whole, not just the individual (Bass, 1996).

Bass and colleagues (Avolio, Bass and Jung, 1995; 1999) pointed out the factors of transformational leadership: influence, inspiration, intellectual stimulation, personal attention. The Transformational leaders are those who develop, excite, and inspire their followers to work to exceed their expectations by eliciting higher levels of their needs. , build trust and put organizational interests above personal interests (Avolio, Waldman Yammarino, 1991; Bass, 1985).

Since the late 1980s Transformational leadership theory has gained popularity in the field of leadership. This theory places an emphasis on emotions and values to demonstrate how a leader has the ability to influence and promote organizational growth. According to Yukl (1989), transformational leadership is defined as a process that greatly influences changes in the attitudes and assumptions of organizational members and builds commitment to the organization's mission and goals.

The relationship between transformational leaders and employees is characterized by pride and respect. Employees proudly assert themselves with the leader and are loyal to the leader (Bass and Avolio, 1990a).

Transformational leadership does not provide solutions and directs employees to implement them, but encourages employees to solve problems independently (Buhler, 1995). Bass and Avolio (1994) argue that behavior encourages employees to independently solve problems make employees more capable of solving problems. Yamarino et al. (1995) also suggested that leaders will take high risks because they put their trust in employees. But if employees understand, they are willing to strive more for the organization (Avolio et al., 1991).

The characteristic of the transformational leadership style is that the leader is never satisfied with the current results. Transformational leaders seek and create meaningful and valuable changes to the organization's mission and vision. Especially, in the context of many social changes, the explosion of knowledge, economic, cultural, political, social environment, leaders are facing enormous opportunities and challenges with the existence and development of communities and organizations. To exploit the opportunities well and adequately handle the challenges, transformational leadership style is well suited to today's volatile environment. At the same time, the leader directs employees to participate in change to develop the organization by inspiring and stimulating creativity. Throughout the leadership process, transformational leaders accomplish tasks by challenging and transforming individuals' emotions, values, ethics, standards, and long-term goals through nurturing charisma. trust and broaden its horizons further (Northouse, 2007).

2.2. Motivation to work

Pinder (1998) states that work motivation is defined as the set of resources originating from within or outside of an individual that creates, guides and maintains people's work-related behavior. According to Robbins (1993), work motivation is the willingness to exert a high degree of effort towards organizational goals.

Campbell and Pritchard (1976) suggest that work motivation consists of a diverse set of interdependent and interdependent relationships that explain direction, skills, understanding of tasks, and activities. that individuals are reluctant to perform in the work environment. Work motivation also refers to the basic psychological state that leads to the behavior and behavior of employees. In general, work motivation is the need, want or desire that takes place inside each employee, causing them to manifest in behavior.

In summary, the researches have the view that: Motivation has personal factors, comes from within the human mind, it is motivated and affected by internal and external factors from the environment. workers' work.

In this study, motivation is understood as an important factor in human resource management that encourages people to work at their best. A strong, positive motivation will help increase work efficiency to help the unit achieve common goals.

2.3. Job performance

Performance is an important issue related to organizational outputs and success (Campbell, 1990). Today, the world is changing day by day, work efficiency is also changing in terms of goals when it is not only a concept of performance but also a requirement for performance (Ilgen and Pulakos, 1999). Evaluation of job performance, two-opinion based studies on performance appraisals based on feedback from managers, colleagues or from more objective sources (Staples et al., 1999) and

appraisals effectiveness is based on respondents' beliefs about job performance (Staples et al., 1999).

In Campbell's (1990) study, eight job performance scores were found as (1) Proficiency in specific tasks; (2) Qualification duties for specific jobs; (3) Written and oral communication; (4) Show effort; (5) Maintain personal discipline; (6) Maintain fairness and efficiency of the work team; (7) Supervision/leadership; and (8) Management. According to Campbell (1990), although these factors may not be available for all jobs, job performance can be assessed through these factors. Depending on the type of work, these elements can be interchangeable.

High efficiency not only brings benefits and opportunities to individuals, but also benefits the organization. High-performing individuals can help companies achieve their goals, increasing their competitive advantage (Sonnetag and Frese, 2002). Work performance in this study is considered an individual's output as assessed by the individual's perception of their job performance.

2.4. Research hypothesis and research model

2.4.1. The relationship between transformational leadership style and job performance

According to Cummings and Schawab (1973), when comparing all organizational factors that affect employees, leadership style is the first factor to be considered. That comes from the fact that the leader has a direct influence on employees in their daily work. A leader is someone who has the ability to persuade and influence others to accomplish desired goals. In other words, leadership is more about the people aspect to unite employees into a team and motivate them towards the desired goals of the organization. Therefore, Bass and Avolio (1994) argue that when a leader possesses a different leadership style, it is an important factor affecting the performance of employees to help the organization succeed. Lashbrook (1997) argues that leadership style plays an important role in influencing employee performance. Some researchers also agree that different leadership styles will create different working environments and directly affect employee performance (Bogler, 2001, 2002).

Watson (2009) argued that although factors such as salary and benefits are important, the most decisive factor affecting employee job satisfaction is the positive relationship between employees and employees. action and leadership (Wagner, 2006). According to Miles and Mangold (2002) job satisfaction is facilitated by the effective monitoring of followers' leadership interactions. According to Aon Consulting (2011), when employees feel that the work environment is safe, their work is safe and the salary is adequate, it is the relationships between colleagues and leaders that influence to job satisfaction and higher organizational loyalty.

The behavior of employees towards their leader will depend on the personality of that employee as well as that of the leader (Wexley and Yukl, 1984). The nature of the employee-leader relationship will greatly affect job performance (Chen, Spector, and Jex 1991). Employees are more effective when leaders think skillfully and encourage employees than leaders who just give orders without thinking to subordinates (Yukl, 1971). The deterioration of employee-leadership relationship will increase the employee's intention to leave and reduce work productivity because employees are not comfortable at work (Ribelin, 2003).

Many researchers agree on the influence of leadership style on employee performance. Accordingly, Seashore and Taber (1975) argue that employee performance is affected by the internal environment of the organization, which includes: leadership style, organizational culture, and personal relationships. The effective interaction of a competent leader will result in employee performance levels Miles and Mangold (2002). Hypothesis H1 is proposed:

H1: Transformational leadership style has a positive impact on job performance.

2.4.2 The relationship between transformational leadership style and work motivation

The researchers found a relationship between transformational leadership style and work motivation. According to Paarlberg and Lavigna (2010) argue that one of the main challenges for research on work motivation is that transformational leadership style will affect organizational motivation to work towards achieving results. .

According to Burns (1978), in the field of leadership research shows that leadership has a strong influence. He describes transformational leaders as having the ability to call on employees to serve the leader's purposes. Transformational leaders have the ability to understand the needs of their employees and also create new motivations for employees. Bass (1985) argues that a transformational leader is someone who inspires, intellectually stimulates, motivates employees, directing them beyond personal interests and towards the interests of the group.

Dovood Hayati et al (2013), study "The relationship between transformational leadership style and work engagement of nurses in public hospitals in Khuzestan, Iran". Research results show that employees are more engaged at work when the leader

inspires optimism through a transformational leadership style. Job engagement is an important factor explaining the relationship between leadership style and employee performance for the organization. Transformational leadership style is a motivating factor and has an impact on the service motivation and work engagement of nurses in public hospitals.

In another study, Bass (1985b) conducted a study of 70 senior executives. He showed that transformational leaders are like benevolent fathers who inspire employees. work long hours to meet leader expectations. Transformational leaders encourage employee growth and give them the initiative to serve the organization.

Transformational leadership transforms employees, thereby boosting their motivation (Avolio and Bass, 1998). Studies in the US and Europe have shown that transformational leadership style and work motivation are positively related (Vandenabeele, 2008; Park and Rainey, 2008).

As such, researchers have also demonstrated that transformational leadership style and work motivation have a positive relationship. Transformational leaders develop, inspire, intellectually stimulate, elicit higher levels of employee needs, build trust, and place organizational interests at stake. above personal interests, always looking for ways to change towards the future, and orienting employees to be ready for changes for the common good of the organization and to serve the organization wholeheartedly. On the basis of inheriting previous studies, the author proposes the hypothesis:

H2: Transformational leadership style has a positive impact on work motivation.

2.4.3. The relationship between work motivation and work performance

Previous studies have shown that thanks to work motivation, employees are more creative, self-aware and enthusiastic to work, so the work also becomes easier and has good results. Hackman and Oldman (1980) emphasize the positive relationship between work motivation and work performance. Deci and Ryan (2008) also demonstrated the impact of employees' satisfaction with endogenous needs (ability, self-determination, familiarity) on job performance.

Indeed, the role of motivational factors is very important. Work motivation will create satisfaction, commitment and commitment of employees, thereby creating efficiency in work (Neal & Vijay, 2009). Promoting work motivation, especially in a complex business like pharmaceuticals, will not only save money in the long run, but also create the best engagement for employees, thereby contributing to increased productivity. performance for employees.

A highly motivated employee will consider the mission and purpose of his organization the most attractive and important and they will be satisfied in their work (Wright and Pandey, 2007). Kim's study (2012) surveyed 814 Korean officials and employees, the research results showed that work motivation not only has a direct influence on job satisfaction but also affects job satisfaction. positively to work attitudes through leader conformity; and also shows that the work motivation and the suitability of the leader are important independent factors affecting the employee's working attitude.

Vandenabeele (2009) studied the mediating effects of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on job performance. The author has demonstrated the relationships of public service motivation. Public service motivation is related to many different outcome variables, (1) There is an increasing positive association between public service motivation and job performance; (2) Job satisfaction and commitment to the organization are both confirmed as antecedents of job performance and motivation for public service. Accordingly, it can be seen that there is a strong relationship between work motivation and personal achievement of employees in the public sector.

Work motivation motivates people to work enthusiastically in the organization, they are satisfied when doing meaningful work and for the community and society. Work motivation is a powerful factor that helps employees move towards the common interests of the organization, serve the organization and wish to contribute to that benefit by their beliefs, personal values and the development of the organization. office. Job satisfaction is considered a consequence of motivation to work in the public sector, when working in the public sector, workers feel satisfied with what they do because they are serving and helping others. different for the development of the organization, of the country (Pandey and Stazyk, 2008; Perry and Wise, 1990). The direct relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction has been demonstrated by scientists in many countries such as Australia (Taylor, 2008), Belgium (Vandenabeele, 2009), China (Liu, Tang, and Zhu, 2008) and South Korea (Kim, 2012), as well as in the United States (Naff and Crum, 1999). Naff and Crum (1999) demonstrated that individuals with high work motivation have higher job satisfaction than those with low work motivation. When the employees in the organization are highly motivated to work, they will be willing to serve the organization, pursue the common interests of the organization, devote themselves to serving the organization. They are satisfied with their work and expect the organization to create many opportunities to serve the interests of the organization.

On the basis of inheriting previous studies, the author hypothesized: When the employees in the organization are highly motivated to work, they will be willing to serve the organization, pursue the common interests of the organization, devote themselves to serving the organization. They are satisfied with their work and expect the organization to create many opportunities to serve the interests of the organization. On the basis of inheriting previous studies, the author hypothesized: When the employees in the organization are highly motivated to work, they will be willing to serve the organization, pursue the common interests of the organization, devote themselves to serving the organization. They are satisfied with their work and expect the organization to create many opportunities to serve the interests of the organization. On the basis of inheriting previous studies, the author hypothesized:

H3: Work motivation has a positive impact on work performance

Research models

The research model is based on previous studies on analyzing the relationship between transformational leadership style factors, work performance and work motivation. Previous studies show that leadership style has a positive impact on work performance, transformational leadership style has a positive impact on work motivation and work motivation has a positive impact on work performance.

The research model is as follows:

Figure 1. Research models

3. RESEARCH METHODS

To ensure the most effective analysis, the author carried out the research according to the given procedure. On the basis of defining research problems, research objectives and synthesizing related theories, the author synthesizes necessary scales (Draft scale 1). Conduct qualitative research through group discussion for the purpose of adjusting and supplementing the scale, research concepts to clarify the meaning and understand the observed variables (Draft scale 2). Then conduct preliminary quantitative research with 90 surveys to evaluate the correlation coefficient of total variables, check the reliability coefficient Cronbach alpha; EFA analysis to check the load factor, factors, percentage of variance extracted to give the official scale.

The official research was carried out by quantitative method by distributing survey questionnaires to 205 civil servants working under the People's Committee of Cam Lam district. This study is used to test the measurement model as well as the theoretical model and the hypotheses in the model. report results and provide policy implications.

To ensure the reliability of the study, the selection of an appropriate sample size is essential. In principle, the larger the sample size, the more accurate the research results, but for this study due to cost and time constraints, the sample size is determined on the principle of the minimum necessary to ensure reliability. reliability of research.

The author uses non-probability sampling method with convenient sampling form. The reason for choosing this method is because it is easy for respondents to approach, ready to answer the survey as well as less time and cost to collect the information to be researched. According to Hoang Trong and Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc (2008), the number of observed samples is 4 or 5 times the number of variables. To choose the right sample size, for factor analysis (EFA), the minimum sample size is $N \geq 5 \times x$ (where x is the total number of observed variables).

In this study, there are all 17 observed variables that need to be estimated, so the minimum sample size is 85 observations. However, in order to ensure the research results achieve reliability, be more representative and prevent the case of no-answer or incomplete answers, the author chooses a sample size of 230 observations.

The sample was selected according to convenience method by surveying civil servants of different ages. The results

received 216 survey votes, of which 205 were valid and 11 were invalid. Invalid votes will be removed before entering into SPSS software. Therefore, the survey sample selected as 205 observations is suitable for the requirements and representative of the sample, so it is guaranteed for the research implementation.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Research sample

- Gender: In 205 observations, there were 150 women (73%) and 50 men (27%). This result shows that women account for more than men.
- Age: There are 35 people under 30 years old (accounting for 17%), from 30 to 40 people there are 108 people (accounting for 53%), from 41 to 50 there are 30 people (accounting for 15%) and There are 32 people aged 51 and older (accounting for 16%).
- Working seniority: 46 people working for less than 5 years (accounting for 22%), from 5 to under 10 years, 55 people (accounting for 27%), from 10 to under 15 years, 50 people (accounting for rate 24%) and 54 people from 15 years or more (accounting for 26%).

4.2. Analysis of CFA

Confirmatory factor analysis or critical model analysis, also known as the overall measurement model, in which the research concepts are related to each other (Nguyen Dinh Tho & Nguyen Thi Mai Trang, 2011). In this study, the critical model was established by linking the variables in the scale to the CFA model (Figure 2).

Figure 2. CFA results

The results of CFA analysis with the critical model show that this model has statistical value $\chi^2[108] = 299,707$ ($p = 0.000$). If adjusted by degrees of freedom with $CMIN/df = 2,770 < 3$, the compatibility requirement is met. Other indicators such as $TLI = 0.902 > 0.9$; $CFI = 0.922 > 0.9$; and $RMSEA = 0.097 < 0.80$ are satisfactory. The results show that the CFA weights of all observed variables are greater than 0.5. Therefore, it can be concluded that the critical model achieves compatibility with survey data and confirms the unidirectionality and convergence value of the scales used in the research model.

Weight (λ_i) to reach the allowable value (≥ 0.5) and is statistically significant because the p-values are all equal to 0.000. Therefore, the observed variables used to measure the scales achieve convergent values.

4.3. SEM results

This section presents the results of testing the theoretical model and the basic research hypothesis. The theoretical model has 108 degrees of freedom. SEM results show that the model has a Chi-squared of 299,160 ($p = 0.000$). If adjusted for degrees of freedom with $CMIN/df = 2,770 < 3$, the other criteria are satisfactory: $GFI = 0.841$; $TLI = 0.902$; $CFI = 0.922$; $RMSEA = 0.097$. Thus, the SEM results show that the model is compatible with the data. In the SEM model, the Heywood phenomenon (negative error variance) does not appear in the estimation process and most of the standardized residuals are less than $|2.58|$.

The estimated results of the (normalized) theoretical model are shown in Figure 3. These results show that hypotheses H1 to H4 are accepted at 99% confidence.

Figure 3. SEM results

Table 1. Estimation of Regression Weight

Relationship	Unnormalized estimate	Normalized Estimation	SE (β)	Value t	P-value
DL <--- LD	.601	.861	.069	8,755	0.000
HQ <--- DL	.882	.602	.229	3,857	0.000
HQ <--- LD	.293	.286	.146	2,001	0.045

- Hypothesis H1: Transformational leadership style has a positive impact on job performance. The estimation results show that this hypothesis is accepted ($\beta = 0.293$; $p = 0.045 < 5\%$).
- Hypothesis H2: Transformational leadership style has a positive impact on work motivation. The estimation results show that this hypothesis is accepted ($\beta = 0.861$; $p = 0.000 < 1\%$).
- Hypothesis H3: Work motivation has a positive impact on work performance. The estimation results show that this hypothesis is accepted ($\beta = 0.602$; $p = 0.000 < 1\%$).

5. DISCUSSION

Compared with other studies in the world, the results of this study correspond to previous studies and also receive support from the research of Yaghoubipoor et al (2013), Shibru and Darshan (2011), Wright, Moynihan and Pandey (2012), Vandenaabeele, (2008), Park and Rainey, (2008) and some other studies. The components of transformational leadership style, work motivation have a positive relationship to work performance. The author's research results also coincide with some previous domestic studies such as those of Tran Trung Dung (2020), Bui Thi Minh Thu and Le Nguyen Doan Khoi (2014), Hoang Thi Hong Loc (2014), Vu Minh Hung (2017).

About leadership and management capacity: Most of the leaders at the unit fully meet the requirements on mandatory conditions as prescribed (degrees, politics, ethical qualities, working seniority ...) and suitable for the position, title is working. The organization and management are experienced and adept in operating the organization's activities, basically grasp the regulations on the order and procedures for related jobs.

6. CONCLUSION

Through research and analysis of survey data, the author obtained the following main results:

First: The author has compiled personal information of the survey subjects, which is information such as: gender, age, seniority, income, education level. Thereby, the author captures the necessary information about the subjects that he has conducted the survey.

Second: Assessing the reliability of the scales through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, the results show that the scales belonging to the transformational leadership style factors, work motivation and work efficiency all meet the level of success. trust. Specifically, the Cronbach's Alpha value of the transformational leadership style factor is 0.905, the work motivation is 0.887 and the work efficiency is: 0.906.

Third: The results of EFA exploratory factor analysis show that the variables of the transformational leadership style factors, work motivation and work efficiency are all arranged in the same group of factors, with weights. satisfactory (> 0.5), KMO value is greater than 0.5, Sig value is less than 5%, total variance extracted factors are all greater than 50% at eigenvalues greater than 1. Thus, the scales mentioned in the theoretical model meet the requirements of reliability, discriminant value and convergent value should be used in CFA test.

Fourth: The results of CFA analysis with the critical model show that this model has statistical value $\chi^2[106] = 291,707$ ($p = 0.000$), $CMIN/df = 2.752 < 3$ meets the compatibility requirement. Other indicators such as $TLI = 0.903 > 0.9$; $CFI = 0.924 > 0.9$ and $RMSEA = 0.097 < 0.80$ are both satisfactory. The results show that the CFA weights of all observed variables are greater than 0.5. Therefore, it can be concluded that the critical model achieves the compatibility with the survey data and confirms that the observed variables used to measure the scales in the research model achieve the discriminant and the convergent value. capacitor.

Fifth: The results of testing the theoretical model and research hypothesis by AMOS-SEM analysis show that the theoretical model of the relationship between transformational leadership style, work motivation and job performance of employees. civil servants in Cam Lam district are suitable; The research hypotheses proposed in this study are accepted. In particular, through the test results of the intermediate variable, it shows that work motivation is the mediator linking transformational leadership style and work performance. Because there is an indirect effect because the CI interval does not include zero (95% CI: 0.279; 1.065) and the point estimate of the relationship is always within this confidence interval ($\beta = 0.518$ in the range (0.279; 1.065)). Therefore, work motivation plays a part as a mediator between the transformational leadership style and the performance of civil servants. Therefore, transformational leadership style has both a direct impact on work performance and an indirect effect on work performance through the mediating factor of motivation.

Sixth: Descriptive statistics show that all factors of transformational leadership style, work motivation and work performance have an average value of approximately 4 (from 3.99 to 4.33). However, at a low level, there are still some values at level 1 and level 2 at a low level in terms of work efficiency and work motivation, so there is a need for solutions to improve transformational leadership style to create motivation for work. work and work efficiency for civil servants.

REFERENCES

1. Avolio, BJ, Bass, BM, and Jung, DI ,1995. MLQ multifactor leadership questionnaire: Technical Report. Redwood city.CA: Mindgarden.
2. Avolio, Bruce J., David A. Waldman, and Francis J. Yammarino , 1991. The Four I's of Transformational leadership. Journal of European Industrial Training,15 (4): 9-16.
3. Avolio, BJ, Bass, BM, and Jung, DI, 1999. Re-examining the components of transformational and transactional leadership using the multifactor leadership questionnaire. Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology, 72 (4): 441-463.
4. Bass, BM (1990), From transactional to transformational leadership: Learning to share the vision. Organizational Dynamics, 18(3), 19-32.
5. Bass, BM (1985), Leadership and Performance Beyond Expectations.New York: FreePress.
6. Bass, B. M, 1985b. Leadership: Good, better, best. Organizational Dynamics, 13(3), 26-40.
7. Bass, B., and Avolio, B. (1994), Improving Organizational Effectiveness through Transformational Leadership. Sage, California: Thousand Oaks.
8. Bass BM, Avolio BJ (1997), Full range leadership development: manual for the multifactor leadership questionnaire. Palo Alto, USA: Mind Garden Inc..
9. Bass, BM, and Avolio, B. J, 1994, Transformational leadership and organizational culture.International Journal of Public Administration, 17(3), 541-554.
10. Bass, BM, and Avolio, B. J, 2004. Transformational leadership development: Manual for the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire. Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press.
11. Bass, BM, 1996. A New Paradigm of Leadership: An Inquiry into Transformational Leadership. US Alexandria, VA: Army Research Institute for the Behavioral and Social Sciences.
12. Maartje PAAIS1, Jozef R. PATTIRUHU2, 2020. Effect of Motivation, Leadership, and Organizational Culture on Satisfaction and Employee Performance. Asia Business, Economics and Finance Magazine.
13. Maria Lucia Specchia, Maria Rosaria Cozzolino, Andrea Di, Caterina, Walter Ricciardi and Gianfranco Damiani, 2021. Leadership Styles and Nurses' Job Satisfaction. Results of a Systematic Review. Int. J. Environ. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.

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